

Novel Biomodel and Biosimulation to demonstrate the need for resorption in the case of edentulism, does we need bone augmentation for implant or it is mostly a futile procedure?

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon¹, David I Adam²

1 Ashty Teaching Hospital

Erbil, Kurdistan region, Iraq

mzsmaxillofacial@gmail.com

2 OSTEOOTECH UK LIMITED

London – UK

davidibrahamadam@gmail.com

Abstract

Post extraction bone resorption is an eventual process that affect the alveolar processes to various extents. We tried to emulate the resorption of the alveolar process depending upon the stiffness of a dentulous model. Resorption is a perquisite to maintain healthy bone and it must be understood as a more complicated process that just attribute it to the loss of loading transmitted to the alveolar process vis teeth. This is the first time such a model had been presented. This model is based upon the model of jaw weakening caused by the teeth presence with sound healthy PD ligaments components. The current model is of retrograde validation model as the real model is already show resorption as an eventual result of edentulism whether partial or complete. It had shown clearly the importance of the soft teeth attachment to the alveolar process as a macro-mechanical feature to provide excellent stiffness reduction.

Keywords

Alveolar Process Resorption, Bone Augmentation, Finite Element Analysis, Biomechanics, Stiffness, Strain of Bone, Strain Energy Density, Teeth as jaws weakeners, Teeth as stiffness reducers

Introduction

Alveolar process volume (height and width) maintenance in the dentulous status is occur via mechanism totally different from that when implant placed. (1) Mechanical proprieties of the PD ligament act as mechanical response modifier of the jaw. (2) One of the most important issues is the bone resorption that occurring after teeth loss due to the associated difficulty in the subsequent dental

rehabilitation. (3) For many years this resorption had been attributed to the lose of the teeth and the subsequent loss of loading or due to the injury from the old fasion dental rehabilitation namely denture whether complete or partial. (4) Biomechanical process that lead to such event should be disclosed to make any plan for correction precise and effective. (5) Augmentation is questionable procedure by many authors. (6) Many numerical models had been proposed. (7) We don't agree with this model as all overlook the most important aspect which is the global stiffness. (8)

Bone remodeling should be understood under the umbrella of the global stiffness of the jaws, both upper and lower rather than consider the resorption as a local event after tooth loss.

We should always see the whole picture rather than confine ourselves in a diploic vision to go beyond our noses` tips.

We had chosen 2 criteria for evaluation

- Displacement to evaluate the stiffness (9)
- To represent the remodeling event the strain energy density had been chosen (10)

Methods

Figure 1 The dimensions of the cross section of the primary model used to synthesise other models

Figure 2 This the model which is represent elongated version of the previously drawn cross section. The length of the model is 100mm

Figure 3 This is the tooth and the periodontium subdomains

The diameter of the tooth was 4.75 mm and the diameter of the of the socket is 5mm. Accordingly the thickness of the PD is 0.125 mm and the taper of the body of the implant or tooth is 7mm and the end was rounded to reduce stresses concentrations. Rounding the models is a must to prevent stresses concentrations which give shots in the highest values of the post processed results. The distances between the center of each implant or tooth and the center of the next one is 10 mm and the distance from the end was 4mm. All the given numbers are used to introduce representative model for a certain macro-mechanical feature rather than simulate exact copy of the natural model.

The mechanical properties of the model were assigned as:

- PMMA for the bone
- PD ligament as low value shore A rubber silicone
- The dentine was also assigned as PMMA
- The Titanium was chosen as grade 23 high strength alloy

As the differences between the used material the results will be apparently different and indicating the important patterns of the mechanical responses. The model of titanium involved here is to demonstrate the huge shift in the distribution of the stresses and strains within the bone model when the Titanium dental implants are introduced instead of natural tooth or teeth. One side of the model

had been fixed and the other had been exposed to the forces at its upper edge, we think that this is the best arrangement to yield the results that we need to convey our theory about resorption.

Figure 4 The boundaries condition had been demonstrated clearly in this model. The direction of the force was in the -Z direction, in another word it is downward

Results and discussion

Teeth are of paramount importance to the growth. (11) The most effect of the teeth presence on the growth is coming from the presence of the PD component rather than the presence of the teeth and their role in transfer of the load. We here present many criteria of mechanical engineering. The strain criteria to evaluate the most deformable component in the whole domain. (12)

All the next results should be kept in mind in any discussion in the future about biomechanics of the growth and trauma. Presence of the teeth provide significant jaws weakening and this will provide the needed stimulation of the bone.

We attribute bone resorption due to the increased stiffness due to loss of the teeth and filling the socket with continuous bone.

Maintenance of the alveolar bone height after placement of the implant is due to totally different mechanical pathway by stiffening. Accordingly, seeing just the resorbed bone without paying attention to the other criteria should be highly discouraged. Bone augmentation should be only preserved for aesthetic concern only as the bone change will be more globally.

*Essential elements to be introduced as premises before
conclusions are drawn*

In the next model we want to investigate the difference between the

- PD ligaments and osteointegration
- Implant and ankylosed teeth. In the current paper the unresorbed complete healed socket is equal to the ankylosed model
- The difference between natural teeth and titanium implants from the aspect of the difference in the modulus of elasticity and the resultant inherited stiffness

Figure 5 Tooth model displacement

The volume of the bone in the dentulous model (teethed) = 9555.19 cubic millimeters. It is the same as the volume of the implant model. In the implant model, both PD ligaments and the tooth had been assigned with titanium mechanical properties.

Figure 6 Unresorbed edentulous model displacement

The volume of the unresorbed edentulous model (teethless) = 10692.75 cubic millimeters. There is a clear drop in the displacement in the teethed model then from the edentulous and titanium implant model.

Figure 7 Implant model displacement

The volume of the bone in the titanium implants model = 9555.19 cubic millimeters. Implants placement is introducing stiffer component to the osseous structure in addition to this the nature of the connection between the implant and the bone is highly unfavorable.

Figure 8 Tooth model strain energy density

The occurrence of the strain energy density at the outer region could be the explanatory answer for the survival of the thin buccal plate in the case of the anterior teeth. This is a mechanical explanation in addition to the nature of the PD ligament where it is regarded by many histologists as a vascular space which provide excellent vascularity and perfusion. (13)

Figure 9 Unresorbed edentulous model Strain energy density

The deprivation of the bulk of the model from the strain energy density is remarkable. Teeth loss will disturb the strain energy density not just by simply prevent the bone from receiving loads, but also by reduce the voids in the alveolar process.

SIMPLY CONTINUOUS BONE IS LESS FAVORABLE CONDITION THAN THE TEETHED OR WHAT IS CALLED DENTULOUS MODEL

Figure 10 Implant model strain energy density

The deprivation of the outer regions from the strain energy density is stand partially behind the resorption in the buccal or labial plate after titanium implant placement. All the previous and next model, the legend of the results had made been uniform to make the comparison comprehensible and sensible.

In the next cross section of the results of the models, we want to make the differences clearer to the reader.

Figure 11 Cross section of the Strain energy density of the teeth model

Strain energy density is concentrated at the base of the teeth model in contrast to that occurred at the upper part in the case of the titanium dental implants. This distribution is necessary to promote and establish the normal growth of the jaws. These changes extend to involve the basal bone not only the alveolar process.

Figure 12 Cross section of the Strain energy density of the titanium implant model

The lower region of the bone sub-domain in the teeth model as well as the upper region is totally opposite to the model of the titanium dental implants in both regions.

Here a question will emerge **(WHAT IF THE PERIODONTAL RETURN TO THE INITIAL STATUS AFTER THE LOADING?)** this will add an additional strain on the alveolar process that involve the whole jaw, both alveolar process and the basal bone. Although it is very subtle stain but its effect on the long term will be enormous. The molecular biology stands as intermediary actor or executor of the predefined genetic plan. As the load occur on the jaws, the teeth will act as response modifier similar to that occur at the epiphyseal growth plate. This is one of conclusive findings from this paper and it will be discussed in a new supplemental paper.

Figure 13 Strain of the teeth model

The maximum strain had been reached in the PD ligament which is significantly higher than that occurred in the titanium implant model. The highest strain is occurring at the PD ligaments which should be correlated with the vascular nature of the PD ligaments as well as the high cellular turn over from histological point of view. The strain in the deep parts of the teeth model is much lower than that of the titanium implants model.

UP to Here

Figure 14 Strain of the titanium implant model

Figure 14 Strain of the titanium implant model indicate how the disturbance of the strain energy density is occurring in the model of the titanium dental implants in contrast to that of the teeth model. We consider that the increase of stiffness will signal the stage that halt the growth process. The disturbance in stresses ,strains as well as strain energy density had been well correlated in our numerical model about craniosynostosis (14). We should always consider the dark side of the osteointegration. Ankylosis is always a pathological phenomenon.

To make amore comprehensible comparison, we had prepared this graph

Figure 15 (A) strain energy density of the tooth model on the outer surface, (B) cross-section of the strain energy density of the tooth model, (C) Titanium implants models surface energy density, (D) Titanium implants models cross-section energy density

CORE OF THE CURRENT SCIENTIFIC PROPOSAL

Although we hadn't compared in details between the volume between the resorption models as well as the sketch of these model due to the sake of making this paper an introductory paper, but this comparison is still important as we should get parametric approach. In one of the models, we had changed the modulus of elasticity of the material to get less stiffness in order to reach the teethed model displacement. We had fine-tuned the new model to get the desired stiffness. We had not tried the cocktail of the change of dimensions and modulus of elasticity at the same time. We had chosen 2 criteria

- The displacement
- Strain energy density to demonstrate the effect of the macro mechanical differences between the studied models

In order to understand the resorption from biomechanical point of view we had chosen 2 approaches

- 1st path is to reduce the volume of the bone in successive way until reaching the desired stiffness
- 2nd path is to reduce the modulus of elasticity of the bone

In the 2 previous paths, we had fine-tuned the model until we were reaching the displacement of the dentulous model. In many instances the bone, especially the maxillary alveolar process will have enlarged medullary spaces with a marked lipid content.

Alveolar process resorption is biomechanical prerequisite to maintain healthy bone

Figure 16 Models that represent the resorption. These are the cross sections to emulate resorption effect

Figure 17 1st model that mimic resorption

The Volume of the 1st resorption model = 10547.16 cubic millimeters

Figure 18 Displacement of the 1st resorption model

Figure 19 Strain energy of the 1st resorption model

We think that the strain energy density here is of little value as it is not related to the main criteria for evaluation. In the real in vivo model, there will be more generalized uniform change in the bone volume, shape and architecture. This pattern of resorption had been intended to demonstrate the importance of reducing the bone mass by the bone itself to maintain healthy structure.

One of the important features of the facial skeleton is to provide multiple weakening features to prevent trauma from being devastating. This effect of stiffness reduction and the trauma response will be introduced in a separate paper

Figure 20 2nd resorption model. The Volume of the 2nd resorption model = 10327.69 cubic millimeters

Figure 21 2nd resorption model displacement. Increase in the displacement had been introduced

Figure 22 2nd resorption model strain energy density

Figure 23 3rd model of resorption.

The resorption occurs in 3D progression across all models. The volume of the 3d resorption model = 9378.99 cubic millimeters

Figure 24 3rd resorption model displacement

Over reduction will result in excessive displacement and higher reduction in the stiffness.

Figure 25 4th model of resorption.

The resorption occur in 3rd model had been excessive necessitating servo loop feedback. We returned and reduced the reduction in the mass to lesser extent for fine tuning of the stiffness and get a closer displacement to the dentulous model (teethed model). The volume of the 4th model = 9597.71 cubic millimeters.

Figure 26 4th resorption model displacement

The volume of the bone in the dentulous model (teethed) = 9555.19 cubic millimeters. It is

The volume of the unresorbed edentulous model (teethless) = 10692.75 cubic millimeters

The Volume of the 1st resorption model = 10547.16 cubic millimeters

The Volume of the 2nd resorption model = 10327.69 cubic millimeters

The volume of the 3rd resorption model = 9378.99 cubic millimeters

The volume of the 4th model = 9597.71 cubic millimeters

We should notice that the volume of the 4rth model is also in close proximity to the volume of the dentulous model.

We want to donate to a significant point here. The resorption had to be occurred partially due to the fact that the load transmitted to the bone had been missed after teeth loss or after edentulous. Another fact that the oral mucosa is a site for continuous trauma and injury due to need of the patient to eat and feed especially in the case of traumatizing prosthesis is another partial precipitating factor.

Conclusion

According to previous findings we could conclude that:

- Resorption in alveolar process is a adynamic responsive process to the increased stiffness of the bone after filling of the socket with bone. It will be accomplished by the bone itself. It represents a primary need, irrelative to load transferred to the bone by teeth or not, rather than secondary phenomenon
- Loss of the dentition and decrease in the bone volume due to resorption is driven by integral stiffness controlling mechanism in the bone. This reduction in the bone volume due to the resorption might result in severe resorption that could be followed by period of need for more stiffness. This swinging between the need for the reduction of stiffness followed by need for strength increase will push the cortication of the bone ability to its maximum limit resulting in many cases by obliteration of the medullary spaces including encroachment over the space occupied by the inferior alveolar neurovascular bundle.

The simplest example is placement of long implant in the anterior region while the posterior region has a pencil like thickness. This phenomenon is seen in the case of unilateral TMJ ankylosis. The example of cortical hypertrophy in the unilateral ankylotic TMJ will be discussed in another paper *if the God will it will be*.

The volume of the 4rth model is also in close proximity to the volume of the dentulous model. We had successfully produced a model valid for explanation of the resorption. The resorption is intended and programed process that is controlled by autocrine and paracrine affecters and other molecular pathways in addition to the systemic and genetic factors that are integral part of the bone maintenance activity.

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.